

Floral preferences of mountain bumble bees are constrained by trait matching but flexible through elevation and season

Appendix 1: Analytical workflow

Douglas B. Sponsler* Katharina Kallnik Fabrice Requier Alice Classen
A. Fabienne Maihoff Johanna Sieger Ingolf Steffan-Dewenter

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*douglas.sponsler@uni-wuerzburg.de

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1. Overview

This appendix begins with a description of how our data were pre-processed in preparation for analysis. We then discuss some limitations of our sampling and modeling approaches that should be considered when interpreting our results.

The main body of the appendix is a complete analytical workflow that reproduces all results described in our paper, together with detailed model outputs and diagnostics that were not included in the paper. If you want to re-run the analysis, save this file in a directory with its associated data files and run the code blocks in RStudio.

2. Data pre-processing

Prior to analysis, we aligned each visitation sample with a corresponding floral survey sample. In most cases, floral surveying was conducted jointly with bumble bee observation for each site and date. Occasionally, though, floral surveying could not be completed on the same day as bumble bee observation, resulting in a small temporal offset between visitation samples and floral survey samples. In these cases, visitation samples were paired with the nearest available floral survey data within a maximum distance of 7 days. Visitation samples lacking corresponding floral survey data within 7 days were omitted from further analysis, which resulted in dropping 40 site-dates out of a total of 895, leaving 855 site-dates included in our analyses. In a few cases, two consecutive visitation samples at a given site shared the same nearest floral survey sample; in these cases, the visitation samples were first pooled, then aligned to their shared nearest floral survey sample. In rare cases, a given floral species was recorded during visitation sampling but missed during floral surveying, and these species were retroactively assigned the minimum floral area value of 0.01 m². Having thus aligned visitation data and flower cover data, we summed visitation and floral cover across species within each floral morphotype. This yielded, for each of our 855 aligned samples, a cumulative value of flower cover for each floral morphotype and a cumulative value of visitation for each bumble- bee-morphotype pair.

3. Methodological caveats

Some limitations of our sampling and modeling methods should be considered when interpreting the results of our analysis. The inference of selection as use-relative-to-abundance is sensitive to exactly *how* abundance is estimated (Johnson 1980; Beyer *et al.* 2010). Of particular concern in our study is the problem of spatial scale. By necessity, we measured floral abundance and visitation along transects *within* our study sites. Bumble bee foraging range, however, is much larger than our study sites, and it is possible that the relative

abundances of floral morphotypes outside our study sites but within foraging range differ from our within-site estimates. Moreover, because bumble bees can forage across multiple meadow patches in a mountain forest matrix (Mola *et al.* 2020), there exists a prior selective process — Johnson’s (1980) “second-order selection” — in which bumble bees choose among available foraging areas before selecting from resources within an area.

The null modeling approach we use (Vaughan *et al.* 2018) assumes that the probability of a resource being selected is linearly proportional to the relative abundance of the resource. It is possible, however, for resource use to exhibit nonlinear “functional responses” (Mysterud & Ims 1998) to resource abundance, which could cause a linear null model to yield biased estimates of preference.

The topic of competition raises an issue that can confound any observational study of resource selection: how to disentangle the endogenous process of resource preference from the exogenous process of niche partitioning driven by competition (Pianka 1974). Observed visitation patterns could reflect a latent process of resource preference, as we assume in our interpretation. Alternatively, though, preferences inferred from visitation patterns could be distorted by competitive forces. Intraspecific competition in a bumble bee community would tend to force individuals of a species to broaden their diet beyond what they would prefer under non-competitive conditions, while interspecific competition would be expected to cause a narrowing of diet breadth toward resources that can be exploited most efficiently. Thus, observed visitation patterns, even when calculated as abundance-relative preference, can only be interpreted in terms of *preference* to the extent that competition can be assumed to be negligible, and assumption must be justified on the basis of additional knowledge of the study system under consideration. Our study system in the Berchtesgadener Alps is one of abundant floral resources but harsh abiotic conditions, so it is likely that competition for floral resources is low, or at least transient, and that bumble bee populations are limited instead by the shortness of the growing season, as has been suggested in the similar environment of the Eyne Valley of France (Iserbyt *et al.* 2008). We cannot, however, exclude the possibility that competitive forces distort, to some degree, the visitation patterns we observed. Even when competitive conditions do not obtain universally in a given system, competition may occur in a spatially and/or temporally localized way (Ranta & Vepsäläinen 1981), perhaps associated with extreme climatic events that cause reductions in floral resource availability (Rasmont & Iserbyt 2012; Thomson 2016; Phillips *et al.* 2018). This calls to mind the insight of MacArthur1972-qz, that competition need not be frequent to have lasting ecological impacts.

4. Prepare environment

4.1 Packages

```
library(patchwork)
library(econullnetr)
library(mgcv)
library(mgcViz)
library(tidymv)
library(tidytext)
library(tidyverse)
library(lubridate)
library(broom)
library(vegan)
library(ggvegan)
library(ggrepel)
```

4.2 Load data

```
visitation <- readRDS("./visitation.rds")

visitation_workers <- visitation %>%
  filter(caste == "worker")

survey <- read_csv("./floral_survey.csv")

flower_cover_ktype <- readRDS("./flower_cover_ktype.rds")

bb_traits <- read_csv("./bb_traits.csv") %>%
  select(bb.sp, pbl.w, tongue = pbl.w.class2)

site_data <- read_csv("./site_data.csv") %>%
  dplyr::select(-c(slope.calc, slope.est, elev.min, elev.max,
                  temp.mean, elev.class, elev.class2)) %>%
  mutate(site = factor(site),
         tree_line = factor(tree_line))

fl_traits <- readRDS("./fl_traits.rds")

vis_spp <- visitation %>%
  left_join(fl_traits) %>%
  group_by(sample.id, bb.sp, plant.genus, ktype) %>%
  summarize(visits = n()) %>%
  group_by(bb.sp, sample.id) %>%
  mutate(prop.visits = visits/sum(visits))

fl_tax <- read_csv("./floral_tax.csv")
```

4.3 Derive proportional visitation and flower cover

```
visitation_prop <- visitation %>%
  group_by(sample.id, bb.sp, ktype) %>%
  summarize(visits = n()) %>%
  group_by(sample.id, bb.sp) %>%
  mutate(prop.visits = visits/sum(visits)) %>%
  select(sample.id, bb.sp, ktype, prop.visits) %>%
  group_by(bb.sp) %>%
  nest() %>%
  mutate(fill = map(data, function(x)
    full_join(x, flower_cover_ktype) %>%
    replace_na(replace = list(prop.visits = 0)))) %>%
  unnest(fill) %>%
  select(-data) %>%
  group_by(bb.sp, ktype) %>%
  summarize(mean.prop.visits = mean(prop.visits)) %>%
  filter(ktype != 10) %>%
  mutate(ktype = case_when(
    ktype == 0 ~ "null",
```

```

ktype == 1 ~ "disc",
ktype == 2 ~ "funnel",
ktype == 3 ~ "bell",
ktype == 4 ~ "stalk-disc",
ktype == 5 ~ "lip",
ktype == 6 ~ "flag",
ktype == 7 ~ "head",
ktype == 9 ~ "brush"
)) %>%
mutate(ktype = factor(ktype, levels = c("null", "disc", "funnel",
                                       "bell", "stalk-disc", "lip",
                                       "flag", "head", "brush"))) %>%

filter(!ktype %in% c("null", "brush")) %>%
droplevels() %>%
left_join(bb_traits) %>%
ungroup() %>%
mutate(bb.sp = fct_reorder(factor(bb.sp), pbl.w))

visit_cover_sitedate <- visitation %>%
group_by(sample.id, bb.sp, ktype) %>%
summarize(visits = n()) %>%
group_by(sample.id, bb.sp) %>%
mutate(prop.visits = visits/sum(visits)) %>%
select(sample.id, bb.sp, ktype, prop.visits) %>%
group_by(bb.sp) %>%
nest() %>%
mutate(fill = map(data, function(x)
  full_join(x, flower_cover_ktype) %>%
  replace_na(replace = list(prop.visits = 0)))) %>%
unnest(fill) %>%
select(-data) %>%
filter(!ktype %in% c("0", "9")) %>%
droplevels() %>%
left_join(bb_traits) %>%
separate(sample.id, c("site", "date"), sep = "_") %>%
left_join(site_data) %>%
unite(bb.ktype, c(bb.sp, ktype), remove = FALSE) %>%
mutate(date = ymd(date),
       yday = yday(date),
       bb.ktype = factor(bb.ktype),
       site = factor(site),
       year = year(date))

flower_cover_ktype.prop <- flower_cover_ktype %>%
group_by(sample.id) %>%
mutate(prop.cover = cover/sum(cover)) %>%
separate(sample.id, c("site", "date"), sep = "_") %>%
mutate(date = ymd(date),
       yday = yday(date),
       ktype = factor(ktype),
       site = factor(site),
       year = year(date)) %>%
filter(!ktype %in% c("10", "0", "9")) %>% # type 0 were not reliably

```

```

droplevels() %>%
left_join(site_data)
# quantified (and rarely visited)
# and type 9 was vanishingly rare

```

5. Generate null models

5.1 Null model 1: bb.sp x ktype, fully pooled

This takes a long time to run, so I have commented out the model call. The output of the model (well, an output of the model — it’s a stochastic process) saved as “null1.rds” is loaded from storage. If you want to rerun the model, simply uncomment the code block and go make coffee.

```

# The "consumers" table input to generate_null_net()
con <- visitation %>%
  mutate(individual.id = row_number()) %>%
  select(sample.id, individual.id, bb.sp, ktype, visited) %>%
  group_by(sample.id) %>%
  arrange(ktype) %>%
  pivot_wider(values_from = visited, names_from = ktype, values_fill = 0) %>%
  arrange(sample.id) %>%
  ungroup() %>%
  as.data.frame()

# The "resources" table input to generate_null_net()
res <- flower_cover_ktype %>%
  select(sample.id, ktype, cover) %>%
  group_by(sample.id) %>%
  arrange(ktype) %>%
  distinct() %>%
  pivot_wider(values_from = cover, names_from = ktype, values_fill = 0) %>%
  arrange(sample.id) %>%
  ungroup() %>%
  droplevels() %>%
  as.data.frame()

# Generate null model

# null1 <- generate_null_net(consumers = con[, 3:12],
#                             resources = res[, 2:10],
#                             sims = 500, # raised from default of 100
#                             data.type = "names",
#                             c.samples = con[,1], # parsed by sample
#                             r.samples = res[,1],
#                             summary.type = "mean") # summarizing with the mean
#                                                     # instead of the default sum
#                                                     # standardizes across our
#                                                     # bumble bee species that
#                                                     # vary in total abundance,

#
# saveRDS(null1, file = "./null1.rds")

```

```
# Read in saved model output
null1 <- readRDS("./null1.rds")
```

5.6 Null model 1b: bb.sp x ktype, fully pooled (worker caste only)

This model was generated to make sure that the pooling of workers and queens did not bias our analysis significantly. The results of this model are very similar to those of the model that uses the pooled data, so we report only the pooled data model in the paper.

```
# The "consumers" table input to generate_null_net()
con_workers <- visitation_workers %>%
  mutate(individual.id = row_number()) %>%
  select(sample.id, individual.id, bb.sp, ktype, visited) %>%
  group_by(sample.id) %>%
  arrange(ktype) %>%
  pivot_wider(values_from = visited, names_from = ktype, values_fill = 0) %>%
  arrange(sample.id) %>%
  ungroup() %>%
  as.data.frame()

# The "resources" table input to generate_null_net()
res_workers <- flower_cover_ktype %>%
  select(sample.id, ktype, cover) %>%
  group_by(sample.id) %>%
  arrange(ktype) %>%
  distinct() %>%
  pivot_wider(values_from = cover, names_from = ktype, values_fill = 0) %>%
  ungroup() %>%
  droplevels() %>%
  as.data.frame() %>%
  semi_join(con_workers, by = "sample.id") %>%
  arrange(sample.id)

# Generate null model

# null1b <- generate_null_net(consumers = con_workers[, 3:12],
#                             resources = res_workers[, 2:10],
#                             sims = 500,
#                             data.type = "names",
#                             # c.samples = con$sample.id,
#                             # r.samples = res$sample.id,
#                             c.samples = con_workers[,1],
#                             r.samples = res_workers[,1],
#                             summary.type = "mean")

# saveRDS(null1b, file = "./null1b.rds")

null1b <- readRDS("./null1b.rds")
```

5.7 Null model 2: bb.sp x ktype, by site-date

This model fits a separate null model to each site-date, enabling us to explore the variation of preference through elevation and seasonal time. Again, I've commented out the model call and instead load a saved output. To rerun the model, simply uncomment the code block, go to bed, and wake up to the smell of freshly brewed null model.

```
# The "consumers" table input to generate_null_net()
con2 <- visitation %>%
  mutate(individual.id = row_number()) %>%
  select(sample.id, individual.id, bb.sp, ktype, visited) %>%
  group_by(sample.id) %>%
  arrange(ktype) %>%
  pivot_wider(values_from = visited, names_from = ktype, values_fill = 0) %>%
  group_by(sample.id) %>%
  nest() %>%
  rename(bees = data)

# The "resources" table input to generate_null_net()
res2 <- flower_cover_ktype %>%
  select(sample.id, ktype, cover) %>%
  group_by(sample.id) %>%
  arrange(ktype) %>%
  distinct() %>%
  pivot_wider(values_from = cover, names_from = ktype, values_fill = 0) %>%
  group_by(sample.id) %>%
  nest() %>%
  rename(plants = data)

conres2 <- full_join(con2, res2) %>%
  separate(sample.id, c("site", "date"), sep = "_")

# Create a big beautiful table of data and models. Takes about 8 hours to
# run on a capable HPC.

# null2 <- conres2 %>%
#
# # Generate null models
# mutate(null.model = map2(bees, plants, function(x, y)
#   generate_null_net(consumers = x[, 2:11],
#                     resources = y[, 1:9],
#                     sims = 500,
#                     data.type = "names",
#                     prog.count = TRUE,
#                     summary.type = "mean")))

# saveRDS(null2, "./null2.rds") # hpc

null2 <- readRDS("./null2.rds")
```

6. Tabulate null models

6.1 Null model 1

```
# Tabulate output and generate tests
null_tab1 <- test_interactions(null1, signif.level = 0.99) %>% # conservative to
                                                    # account for
                                                    # multiple comparisons

as_tibble() %>%
select(bb.sp = Consumer, ktype = Resource, everything()) %>%
group_by(bb.sp) %>%
mutate(preference = Observed - Null, # a working definition of preference
       preference.upper99 = Observed - Upper.99.CL,
       preference.lower99 = Observed - Lower.99.CL) %>%
left_join(bb_traits) %>%
ungroup() %>%
mutate(bb.sp = fct_reorder(factor(bb.sp), pbl.w)) %>%
mutate(ktype = case_when(
  ktype == 0 ~ "null",
  ktype == 1 ~ "disc",
  ktype == 2 ~ "funnel",
  ktype == 3 ~ "bell",
  ktype == 4 ~ "stalk-disc",
  ktype == 5 ~ "lip",
  ktype == 6 ~ "flag",
  ktype == 7 ~ "head",
  ktype == 9 ~ "brush"
)) %>%
mutate(ktype = factor(ktype, levels = c("null", "disc", "funnel",
                                       "bell", "stalk-disc", "lip",
                                       "flag", "head", "brush"))) %>%
filter(!ktype %in% c("null", "brush")) %>% # type 0 were not reliably quantified
                                                    # (and rarely visited) and type 9
                                                    # was vanishingly rare

droplevels()
```

6.2 Null model 1b

```
# Tabulate output and generate tests
null_tab1b <- test_interactions(null1b, signif.level = 0.99) %>%
as_tibble() %>%
select(bb.sp = Consumer, ktype = Resource, everything()) %>%
group_by(bb.sp) %>%
mutate(preference = Observed - Null,
       preference.upper99 = Observed - Upper.99.CL,
       preference.lower99 = Observed - Lower.99.CL) %>%
left_join(bb_traits) %>%
ungroup() %>%
mutate(bb.sp = fct_reorder(factor(bb.sp), pbl.w)) %>%
mutate(ktype = case_when(
```

```

ktype == 0 ~ "null",
ktype == 1 ~ "disc",
ktype == 2 ~ "funnel",
ktype == 3 ~ "bell",
ktype == 4 ~ "stalk-disc",
ktype == 5 ~ "lip",
ktype == 6 ~ "flag",
ktype == 7 ~ "head",
ktype == 9 ~ "brush"
)) %>%
mutate(ktype = factor(ktype, levels = c("null", "disc", "funnel",
                                       "bell", "stalk-disc", "lip",
                                       "flag", "head", "brush"))) %>%
filter(!ktype %in% c("null", "brush")) %>%
droplevels()

```

6.3 Null model 2

```

# Tabulate results (with test)
null_tab2 <- null2 %>%
mutate(null.model.tab = map(null.model, function(x)
  test_interactions(x, signif.level = 0.95) %>%
  as_tibble() %>%
  mutate(preference = Observed - Null,
         preference.upper95 = Observed - Upper.95.CL,
         preference.lower95 = Observed - Lower.95.CL) %>%
  select(bb.sp = Consumer, ktype = Resource, everything())) %>%

# Unnest and add site data and bumble bee trait data
unnest(null.model.tab) %>%
select(site, date, bb.sp, ktype, Observed, Null, Lower.95.CL, Upper.95.CL, Test,
       SES, preference, preference.upper95, preference.lower95) %>%
left_join(site_data) %>%
left_join(bb_traits) %>%
group_by(site, date, bb.sp) %>%
mutate(total.observed = sum(Observed)) %>% # There are a few cases in which
                                           # total.observed does not equal
                                           # unity. This is because bees
                                           # occasionally visited plants in
                                           # ktypes 0, 9, or 10, which we
                                           # dropped from the data prior to
                                           # null model calculation but after
                                           # calculating proportional visitation.

ungroup() %>%
filter(total.observed > 0) %>% # for each species, drop sites where
                               # the species did not occur

filter(Observed != 0 | Null != 0) %>%
unite(bb.ktype, c(bb.sp, ktype), remove = FALSE) %>%
mutate(ktype = factor(ktype),
       site = factor(site),
       yday = yday(date),

```

```

year = factor(year(date)),
bb.ktype = factor(bb.ktype),
bb.sp = factor(bb.sp, levels = c("jone", "pyre", "soro", "psit",
                                "telu", "lapi", "prat", "mont",
                                "wurf", "muci", "pasc", "hypn",
                                "mend", "hort", "gers"))) %>%

mutate(ktype = case_when(
  ktype == 0 ~ "null",
  ktype == 1 ~ "disc",
  ktype == 2 ~ "funnel",
  ktype == 3 ~ "bell",
  ktype == 4 ~ "stalk-disc",
  ktype == 5 ~ "lip",
  ktype == 6 ~ "flag",
  ktype == 7 ~ "head",
  ktype == 9 ~ "brush"
)) %>%
mutate(ktype = factor(ktype, levels = c("null", "disc", "funnel",
                                       "bell", "stalk-disc", "lip",
                                       "flag", "head", "brush"))) %>%
filter(!ktype %in% c("null", "brush")) %>%
droplevels()

```

7. Analyze null models

7.1 Null models 1 and 1b

7.1.1 Plot observed vs. expected visitation

```

# Full data
ggplot(null_tab1, aes(Observed, ktype)) +
  geom_segment(aes(y = ktype, yend = ktype,
                  x = Lower.99.CL, xend = Upper.99.CL),
              color = "gray40", inherit.aes = FALSE) +
  geom_point(aes(color = Test)) +
  facet_wrap(~fct_rev(bb.sp)) +
  scale_y_discrete(limits = rev) +
  scale_color_manual(values = c("gray40", "#F8766D", "#00B6EB")) +
  labs(x = "Mean visitation rate", y = "Floral morphotype", color = "Test (p < 0.01)") +
  theme_light()

```



```

# Workers only
ggplot(null_tab1b, aes(Observed, ktype)) +
  geom_segment(aes(y = ktype, yend = ktype,
                  x = Lower.99.CL, xend = Upper.99.CL),
              color = "gray40", inherit.aes = FALSE) +
  geom_point(aes(color = Test)) +
  facet_wrap(~fct_rev(bb.sp)) +
  scale_y_discrete(limits = rev) +
  scale_color_manual(values = c("gray40", "#F8766D", "#00B6EB")) +
  labs(x = "Mean visitation rate", y = "Floral morphotype", color = "Test ( $p < 0.01$ )") +
  theme_light() +
  ggtitle("Workers only")

```


7.1.2 Plot community-level preference and visitation across morphotypes

```
# Full data
null1_plot1 <- ggplot(null_tab1, aes(ktype, preference)) +
  geom_boxplot(fill = NA, color = "black", outlier.shape = NA, size = 0.35) +
  geom_jitter(aes(color = Test), width = 0.3, alpha = 0.6) +
  theme_light(12) +
  scale_color_manual(values = c("gray40", "#F8766D", "#00B6EB")) +
  labs(x = "Floral morphotype",
       y = "Preference")

# Observed visitation
raw_visits_plot1 <- ggplot(visitation_prop, aes(ktype, mean.prop.visits)) +
  geom_boxplot(fill = NA, color = "black", outlier.shape = NA, size = 0.35) +
  geom_jitter(width = 0.3, alpha = 0.5, color = "gray40") +
  theme_light(10) +
  labs(x = "Floral morphotype",
       y = "Mean proportional visitation")

# Comparison of inferred preference and observed visitation
(null1_plot1 / raw_visits_plot1) + plot_annotation(tag_levels = 'A') +
  ggtitle("Workers + queens")
```



```
# Workers only
ggplot(null_tab1b, aes(ktype, preference)) +
  geom_boxplot(fill = NA, color = "black", outlier.shape = NA, size = 0.35) +
  geom_jitter(aes(color = Test), width = 0.3, alpha = 0.6) +
  theme_light(10) +
  scale_color_manual(values = c("gray40", "#F8766D", "#00B6EB")) +
  labs(x = "Floral morphotype",
       y = "Preference") +
  ggtitle("Workers only")
```


7.1.3 GAM analysis of preference and visitation as function of tongue length

```

# Preference: full data
gam1 <- gam(preference ~
  ktype +
  s(pbl.w, by = ktype, k = 5),
  data = null_tab1) %>% getViz()

# Preference: workers only
gam1b <- gam(preference ~
  ktype +
  s(pbl.w, by = ktype, k = 5),
  data = null_tab1b) %>% getViz()

# Observed visitation: full data
gam1c <- gam(mean.prop.visits ~
  ktype +
  s(pbl.w, by = ktype, k = 5),
  family = betar(eps = 0.001),
  data = visitation_prop) %>% getViz()

```

7.1.4 Evaluate GAMs

```
gam1_sum <- summary(gam1)
check.gamViz(gam1)
```

```
##
## Method: GCV   Optimizer: magic
## Smoothing parameter selection converged after 9 iterations.
## The RMS GCV score gradient at convergence was 1.640689e-08 .
## The Hessian was positive definite.
## Model rank = 35 / 35
##
## Basis dimension (k) checking results. Low p-value (k-index<1) may
## indicate that k is too low, especially if edf is close to k'.
##
##           k'   edf k-index p-value
## s(pbl.w):ktypedisc      4.00 1.00   1.08  0.79
## s(pbl.w):ktypefunnel    4.00 1.34   1.08  0.77
## s(pbl.w):ktypebell      4.00 2.96   1.08  0.78
## s(pbl.w):ktypestalk-disc 4.00 1.00   1.08  0.72
## s(pbl.w):ktypelip       4.00 1.30   1.08  0.73
## s(pbl.w):ktypeflag      4.00 3.04   1.08  0.78
## s(pbl.w):ktypehead     4.00 2.06   1.08  0.73
```



```
gam1_sum
```

```
##
## Family: gaussian
## Link function: identity
##
## Formula:
## preference ~ ktype + s(pbl.w, by = ktype, k = 5)
##
## Parametric coefficients:
##           Estimate Std. Error t value Pr(>|t|)
## (Intercept)  -0.24559    0.02232 -11.001 < 2e-16 ***
## ktypefunnel   0.25926    0.03157   8.212 2.07e-12 ***
## ktypebell     0.35454    0.03157  11.230 < 2e-16 ***
## ktypestalk-disc 0.22475    0.03157   7.119 3.19e-10 ***
## ktypelip      0.38627    0.03157  12.235 < 2e-16 ***
## ktypeflag     0.33436    0.03157  10.591 < 2e-16 ***
## ktypehead     0.20596    0.03157   6.524 4.65e-09 ***
## ---
## Signif. codes:  0 '***' 0.001 '**' 0.01 '*' 0.05 '.' 0.1 ' ' 1
##
## Approximate significance of smooth terms:
##           edf Ref.df    F  p-value
## s(pbl.w):ktypedisc    1.000  1.000  0.073 0.788094
## s(pbl.w):ktypefunnel  1.341  1.599  6.922 0.008976 **
## s(pbl.w):ktypebell    2.962  3.436  6.635 0.000224 ***
## s(pbl.w):ktypestalk-disc 1.000  1.000  0.380 0.539186
## s(pbl.w):ktypelip     1.304  1.541  3.592 0.028448 *
## s(pbl.w):ktypeflag    3.041  3.506  7.331 9.49e-05 ***
## s(pbl.w):ktypehead    2.059  2.505  7.858 0.000449 ***
## ---
## Signif. codes:  0 '***' 0.001 '**' 0.01 '*' 0.05 '.' 0.1 ' ' 1
##
## R-sq.(adj) = 0.728  Deviance explained = 77.7%
## GCV = 0.0092021  Scale est. = 0.007475  n = 105
```

```
gam1b_sum <- summary(gam1b)
check.gamViz(gam1b)
```

```
##
## Method: GCV  Optimizer: magic
## Smoothing parameter selection converged after 10 iterations.
## The RMS GCV score gradient at convergence was 1.597488e-08 .
## The Hessian was positive definite.
## Model rank = 35 / 35
##
## Basis dimension (k) checking results. Low p-value (k-index<1) may
## indicate that k is too low, especially if edf is close to k'.
##
##           k'  edf k-index p-value
## s(pbl.w):ktypedisc    4.00 1.00   1.04   0.64
## s(pbl.w):ktypefunnel  4.00 1.61   1.04   0.66
```

```
## s(pbl.w):ktypebell      4.00 2.88    1.04    0.64
## s(pbl.w):ktypestalk-disc 4.00 1.00    1.04    0.57
## s(pbl.w):ktypelip      4.00 1.94    1.04    0.61
## s(pbl.w):ktypeflag     4.00 2.93    1.04    0.58
## s(pbl.w):ktypehead     4.00 1.91    1.04    0.60
```



```
gam1b_sum
```

```
##
## Family: gaussian
## Link function: identity
##
## Formula:
## preference ~ ktype + s(pbl.w, by = ktype, k = 5)
##
## Parametric coefficients:
##              Estimate Std. Error t value Pr(>|t|)
## (Intercept)  -0.22248   0.02342  -9.501 1.20e-14 ***
## ktypefunnel   0.24242   0.03312   7.320 1.96e-10 ***
## ktypebell     0.27690   0.03312   8.361 1.92e-12 ***
## ktypestalk-disc 0.20632   0.03312   6.230 2.23e-08 ***
## ktypelip      0.37880   0.03312  11.438 < 2e-16 ***
## ktypeflag     0.31511   0.03312   9.515 1.12e-14 ***
## ktypehead     0.15821   0.03312   4.777 8.23e-06 ***
## ---
```

```
## Signif. codes:  0 '***' 0.001 '**' 0.01 '*' 0.05 '.' 0.1 ' ' 1
##
## Approximate significance of smooth terms:
##           edf Ref.df    F  p-value
## s(pbl.w):ktypedisc      1.000  1.000  0.015  0.902678
## s(pbl.w):ktypefunnel    1.609  1.975  6.941  0.002751 **
## s(pbl.w):ktypebell      2.884  3.365  3.538  0.012483 *
## s(pbl.w):ktypestalk-disc 1.000  1.000  0.023  0.881086
## s(pbl.w):ktypelip       1.945  2.377  1.428  0.199601
## s(pbl.w):ktypeflag      2.930  3.409  6.750  0.000248 ***
## s(pbl.w):ktypehead      1.913  2.341  4.311  0.013576 *
## ---
## Signif. codes:  0 '***' 0.001 '**' 0.01 '*' 0.05 '.' 0.1 ' ' 1
##
## R-sq.(adj) =  0.689   Deviance explained = 75.1%
## GCV = 0.0096809   Scale est. = 0.0076775   n = 98
```

```
gam1c_sum <- summary(gam1c)
check.gamViz(gam1c)
```

```
##
## Method: REML   Optimizer: outer newton
## full convergence after 10 iterations.
## Gradient range [-2.272452e-05,-8.104628e-15]
## (score -255.2721 & scale 1).
## Hessian positive definite, eigenvalue range [9.121409e-06,36.65468].
## Model rank =  35 / 35
##
## Basis dimension (k) checking results. Low p-value (k-index<1) may
## indicate that k is too low, especially if edf is close to k'.
##
##           k'   edf k-index p-value
## s(pbl.w):ktypedisc      4.00  1.00   0.48 <2e-16 ***
## s(pbl.w):ktypefunnel    4.00  1.00   0.48 <2e-16 ***
## s(pbl.w):ktypebell      4.00  1.00   0.48 <2e-16 ***
## s(pbl.w):ktypestalk-disc 4.00  1.00   0.48 <2e-16 ***
## s(pbl.w):ktypelip       4.00  1.00   0.48 <2e-16 ***
## s(pbl.w):ktypeflag      4.00  2.02   0.48 <2e-16 ***
## s(pbl.w):ktypehead      4.00  1.00   0.48 <2e-16 ***
## ---
## Signif. codes:  0 '***' 0.001 '**' 0.01 '*' 0.05 '.' 0.1 ' ' 1
```



```
gam1c_sum
```

```
##
## Family: Beta regression(18.696)
## Link function: logit
##
## Formula:
## mean.prop.visits ~ ktype + s(pbl.w, by = ktype, k = 5)
##
## Parametric coefficients:
##             Estimate Std. Error z value Pr(>|z|)
## (Intercept)  -3.57593   0.23651 -15.119 < 2e-16 ***
## ktypefunnel  -0.10819   0.33662  -0.321  0.74791
## ktypebell     0.35740   0.32479   1.100  0.27115
## ktypestalk-disc -0.09246   0.33667  -0.275  0.78360
## ktypelip      0.85089   0.31096   2.736  0.00621 **
## ktypeflag     0.52588   0.32031   1.642  0.10064
## ktypehead     0.43294   0.32216   1.344  0.17899
## ---
## Signif. codes:  0 '***' 0.001 '**' 0.01 '*' 0.05 '.' 0.1 ' ' 1
##
## Approximate significance of smooth terms:
##             edf Ref.df Chi.sq p-value
## s(pbl.w):ktypedisc    1.00  1.000  0.558  0.4550
## s(pbl.w):ktypefunnel  1.00  1.000  0.923  0.3367
## s(pbl.w):ktypebell    1.00  1.000  2.574  0.1087
```

```
## s(pbl.w):ktypestalk-disc 1.00 1.000 0.043 0.8355
## s(pbl.w):ktypelip 1.00 1.000 0.051 0.8217
## s(pbl.w):ktypeflag 2.02 2.471 2.658 0.3650
## s(pbl.w):ktypehead 1.00 1.000 3.940 0.0472 *
## ---
## Signif. codes: 0 '***' 0.001 '**' 0.01 '*' 0.05 '.' 0.1 ' ' 1
##
## R-sq.(adj) = 0.053 Deviance explained = 25%
## -REML = -255.27 Scale est. = 1 n = 105
```

7.1.5 Tabulate GAMs

```
# Inverse link function for beta model of observed visitation
inv_logit <- function(x) {
  exp(x)/(1+exp(x))
}

# Tabulate model summary
gam1_s_table <- gam1_sum$s.table %>%
  as.data.frame() %>%
  rownames_to_column("term") %>%
  mutate(ktype = str_extract(term, "(?<=ktype).*\$")) %>%
  mutate(pval = signif(`p-value`, digits = 3)) %>%
  select(ktype, edf, pval) %>%
  as_tibble() %>%
  mutate(ktype = factor(ktype))

gam1b_s_table <- gam1b_sum$s.table %>%
  as.data.frame() %>%
  rownames_to_column("term") %>%
  mutate(ktype = str_extract(term, "(?<=ktype).*\$")) %>%
  mutate(pval = signif(`p-value`, digits = 3)) %>%
  select(ktype, edf, pval) %>%
  as_tibble() %>%
  mutate(ktype = factor(ktype))

gam1c_s_table <- gam1c_sum$s.table %>%
  as.data.frame() %>%
  rownames_to_column("term") %>%
  mutate(ktype = str_extract(term, "(?<=ktype).*\$")) %>%
  mutate(pval = signif(`p-value`, digits = 3)) %>%
  select(ktype, edf, pval) %>%
  as_tibble() %>%
  mutate(ktype = factor(ktype))

# Extract predictions
gam1_pred <- predict_gam(gam1) %>%
  mutate(fit.plus.se = fit + (2*se.fit),
         fit.minus.se = fit - (2*se.fit)) %>%
  left_join(gam1_s_table) %>%
  mutate(sig = if_else(pval < 0.05, TRUE, FALSE)) %>%
  mutate(sig = factor(sig, levels = c(TRUE, FALSE)))
```

```

gam1b_pred <- predict_gam(gam1b) %>%
  mutate(fit.plus.se = fit + (2*se.fit),
         fit.minus.se = fit - (2*se.fit)) %>%
  left_join(gam1_s_table) %>%
  mutate(sig = if_else(pval < 0.05, TRUE, FALSE)) %>%
  mutate(sig = factor(sig, levels = c(TRUE, FALSE)))

gam1c_pred <- predict_gam(gam1c) %>%
  mutate(fit.plus.se = inv_logit(fit + (2*se.fit)),
         fit.minus.se = inv_logit(fit - (2*se.fit)),
         fit = inv_logit(fit)) %>%
  left_join(gam1b_s_table) %>%
  mutate(sig = if_else(pval < 0.05, TRUE, FALSE)) %>%
  mutate(sig = factor(sig, levels = c(TRUE, FALSE)))

```

7.1.6 Plot GAMs

```

null1_plot2 <- ggplot(gam1_pred, aes(pbl.w, fit)) +
  geom_line(aes(linetype = sig)) + # fit line, linetype for significance
  geom_ribbon(aes(ymin = fit.minus.se, ymax = fit.plus.se), # Uncertainty
            fill = "black", alpha = 0.2) +
  geom_point(data = null_tab1, # Original data
            aes(pbl.w, preference, color = bb.sp),
            inherit.aes = FALSE, alpha = 0.5) +
  facet_wrap(~ktype) +
  labs(x = "Tongue length (mm)", y = "Preference",
       color = "Species", linetype = "p < 0.05") +
  scale_x_continuous(breaks = c(7, 10, 13, 16)) +
  theme_light(10)

null1c_plot2 <- ggplot(gam1c_pred, aes(pbl.w, fit)) +
  geom_line(aes(linetype = sig)) + # fit line, linetype for significance
  geom_ribbon(aes(ymin = fit.minus.se, ymax = fit.plus.se), # Uncertainty
            fill = "black", alpha = 0.2) +
  geom_point(data = visitation_prop, # Original data
            aes(pbl.w, mean.prop.visits, color = bb.sp),
            inherit.aes = FALSE, alpha = 0.5) +
  facet_wrap(~ktype) +
  labs(x = "Tongue length (mm)", y = "Visitation rate",
       color = "Species", linetype = "p < 0.05") +
  scale_x_continuous(breaks = c(7, 10, 13, 16)) +
  theme_light(10)

(null1_plot2 | null1c_plot2) +
  plot_layout(guides = "collect") +
  plot_annotation(tag_levels = 'A') +
  ggtitle("Workers + queens")

```

A

B


```
ggplot(gam1_pred, aes(pbl.w, fit)) +
  geom_line(aes(linetype = sig)) + # fit line, linetype for significance
  geom_ribbon(aes(ymin = fit.minus.se, ymax = fit.plus.se), # Uncertainty
            fill = "black", alpha = 0.2) +
  geom_point(data = null_tab1b, # Original data
            aes(pbl.w, preference, color = bb.sp),
            inherit.aes = FALSE, alpha = 0.5) +
  facet_wrap(~ktype) +
  labs(x = "Tongue length (mm)", y = "Preference",
       color = "Species", linetype = "p < 0.05") +
  scale_x_continuous(breaks = c(7, 10, 13, 16)) +
  theme_light(10) +
  ggtitle("Workers only")
```


7.2 Null model 2

GAM analysis of preference, proportional floral cover, and observed visitation through elevation and time. Note that the visitation model is not included in the main paper.

7.2.1 Call GAMs

```
gam_preference <- bam(preference ~
  bb.ktype +
  s(site, by = bb.ktype, bs = "re") +
  s(year, by = bb.ktype, bs = "re") +
  te(yday, elev.mean, by = bb.ktype),
  family = "gaussian",
  method = "fREML",
  discrete = TRUE,
  data = filter(null_tab2,
    bb.sp %in% c("hort", "prat", "telu",
      "wurf", "soro", "pasc") &
    ktype %in% c("bell", "lip", "flag", "head"))) %>%
  getViz()

gam_fl_abund <- bam(prop.cover ~
  ktype +
```

```

      s(site, by = ktype, bs = "re") +
      s(year, by = ktype, bs = "re") +
      te(yday, elev.mean, by = ktype),
    family = betar(),
    method = "fREML",
    discrete = TRUE,
    data = filter(flower_cover_ktype.prop,
                  ktype %in% c("3", "5", "6", "7"))) %>%
getViz()

gam_visitation <- bam(prop.visits ~
  bb.ktype +
  s(site, by = bb.ktype, bs = "re") +
  s(year, by = bb.ktype, bs = "re") +
  te(yday, elev.mean, by = bb.ktype),
  family = "binomial",
  method = "fREML",
  discrete = TRUE,
  data = filter(visit_cover_sitedate,
                bb.sp %in% c("pasc", "prat", "telu", "hort",
                             "soro", "wurf") &
                ktype %in% c("3", "5", "6", "7"))) %>%
getViz()

```

7.2.2 Evaluate GAMs

Note that we are making the evaluation plots manually rather than using `gam.check()` or `check.gamViz()`. The output of `check.gamViz` is verbose and produces extremely printouts for complex models. If you want to see the full output, uncomment the `check.gamViz()` call.

7.2.2.1 Preference GAM

```

##
## Family: gaussian
## Link function: identity
##
## Formula:
## preference ~ bb.ktype + s(site, by = bb.ktype, bs = "re") + s(year,
##   by = bb.ktype, bs = "re") + te(yday, elev.mean, by = bb.ktype)
##
## Parametric coefficients:
##               Estimate Std. Error t value Pr(>|t|)
## (Intercept)   0.046821  0.034630   1.352 0.176390
## bb.ktypehort_5 0.133110  0.083311   1.598 0.110135
## bb.ktypehort_6 0.044693  0.062211   0.718 0.472519
## bb.ktypehort_7 -0.203620  0.045168  -4.508 6.63e-06 ***
## bb.ktypepasc_3 -0.026989  0.038792  -0.696 0.486605
## bb.ktypepasc_5  0.188607  0.058615   3.218 0.001297 **
## bb.ktypepasc_6  0.243552  0.066105   3.684 0.000231 ***
## bb.ktypepasc_7 -0.140586  0.048811  -2.880 0.003983 **

```

```

## bb.ktypeprat_3 0.005399 0.068859 0.078 0.937509
## bb.ktypeprat_5 0.092270 0.071990 1.282 0.199983
## bb.ktypeprat_6 -0.099692 0.041449 -2.405 0.016186 *
## bb.ktypeprat_7 -0.050384 0.053461 -0.942 0.345995
## bb.ktypesoro_3 0.138462 0.083276 1.663 0.096410 .
## bb.ktypesoro_5 0.002938 0.054400 0.054 0.956930
## bb.ktypesoro_6 -0.057454 0.053760 -1.069 0.285226
## bb.ktypesoro_7 0.096813 0.082467 1.174 0.240440
## bb.ktypetelu_3 0.058259 0.044229 1.317 0.187798
## bb.ktypetelu_5 0.063461 0.057468 1.104 0.269505
## bb.ktypetelu_6 0.033075 0.091874 0.360 0.718850
## bb.ktypetelu_7 -0.093868 0.045419 -2.067 0.038789 *
## bb.ktypewurf_3 0.007161 0.043860 0.163 0.870311
## bb.ktypewurf_5 0.016512 0.090718 0.182 0.855579
## bb.ktypewurf_6 0.166033 0.061512 2.699 0.006964 **
## bb.ktypewurf_7 -0.162669 0.053326 -3.050 0.002292 **
## ---
## Signif. codes: 0 '***' 0.001 '**' 0.01 '*' 0.05 '.' 0.1 ' ' 1
##
## Approximate significance of smooth terms:
##
## edf Ref.df F p-value
## te(yday,elev.mean):bb.ktypehort_3 6.424 8.114 2.037 0.037932 *
## te(yday,elev.mean):bb.ktypehort_5 12.895 15.168 4.677 < 2e-16 ***
## te(yday,elev.mean):bb.ktypehort_6 6.127 7.050 3.638 0.000647 ***
## te(yday,elev.mean):bb.ktypehort_7 4.757 5.924 0.770 0.594753
## te(yday,elev.mean):bb.ktypepasc_3 3.000 3.001 3.891 0.008612 **
## te(yday,elev.mean):bb.ktypepasc_5 11.791 14.153 4.561 < 2e-16 ***
## te(yday,elev.mean):bb.ktypepasc_6 12.569 14.913 5.135 < 2e-16 ***
## te(yday,elev.mean):bb.ktypepasc_7 7.302 8.067 5.626 < 2e-16 ***
## te(yday,elev.mean):bb.ktypeprat_3 13.654 16.077 9.289 < 2e-16 ***
## te(yday,elev.mean):bb.ktypeprat_5 10.139 12.116 8.464 < 2e-16 ***
## te(yday,elev.mean):bb.ktypeprat_6 3.000 3.000 1.328 0.263197
## te(yday,elev.mean):bb.ktypeprat_7 8.527 10.324 6.211 < 2e-16 ***
## te(yday,elev.mean):bb.ktypesoro_3 12.986 15.230 6.565 < 2e-16 ***
## te(yday,elev.mean):bb.ktypesoro_5 6.961 8.862 3.057 0.001171 **
## te(yday,elev.mean):bb.ktypesoro_6 6.132 7.235 1.655 0.086573 .
## te(yday,elev.mean):bb.ktypesoro_7 11.141 13.594 1.980 0.012046 *
## te(yday,elev.mean):bb.ktypetelu_3 6.317 7.305 8.223 < 2e-16 ***
## te(yday,elev.mean):bb.ktypetelu_5 9.549 11.796 6.131 < 2e-16 ***
## te(yday,elev.mean):bb.ktypetelu_6 9.460 11.704 3.395 7.93e-05 ***
## te(yday,elev.mean):bb.ktypetelu_7 5.145 6.419 0.986 0.443580
## te(yday,elev.mean):bb.ktypewurf_3 5.173 6.641 3.689 0.000590 ***
## te(yday,elev.mean):bb.ktypewurf_5 14.548 16.764 9.298 < 2e-16 ***
## te(yday,elev.mean):bb.ktypewurf_6 10.368 12.184 11.430 < 2e-16 ***
## te(yday,elev.mean):bb.ktypewurf_7 11.025 13.748 4.138 < 2e-16 ***
## ---
## Signif. codes: 0 '***' 0.001 '**' 0.01 '*' 0.05 '.' 0.1 ' ' 1
##
## R-sq.(adj) = 0.33 Deviance explained = 36.4%
## fREML = 2252.7 Scale est. = 0.085663 n = 9337

```


Histogram of residuals

Resids vs. linear pred.

Response vs. Fitted Values

7.2.2.2 Flower cover GAM

```
##
## Family: Beta regression(9.505)
## Link function: logit
##
## Formula:
## prop.cover ~ ktype + s(site, by = ktype, bs = "re") + s(year,
##   by = ktype, bs = "re") + te(yday, elev.mean, by = ktype)
##
## Parametric coefficients:
##           Estimate Std. Error t value Pr(>|t|)
## (Intercept) -185.57    85.17  -2.179  0.0294 *
## ktype5       183.63    85.17   2.156  0.0312 *
## ktype6       183.15    85.17   2.150  0.0316 *
## ktype7       183.90    85.17   2.159  0.0309 *
## ---
## Signif. codes:  0 '***' 0.001 '**' 0.01 '*' 0.05 '.' 0.1 ' ' 1
##
## Approximate significance of smooth terms:
##           edf Ref.df    F p-value
## te(yday,elev.mean):ktype3 20.15  21.37 39.95 <2e-16 ***
## te(yday,elev.mean):ktype5 14.04  16.36 38.59 <2e-16 ***
```

```
## te(yday,elev.mean):ktype6 16.99 19.04 13.21 <2e-16 ***
## te(yday,elev.mean):ktype7 17.13 19.09 21.88 <2e-16 ***
## ---
## Signif. codes:  0 '***' 0.001 '**' 0.01 '*' 0.05 '.' 0.1 ' ' 1
##
## R-sq.(adj) = 0.554  Deviance explained = 64.3%
## fREML = -1074.4  Scale est. = 1          n = 3161
```


Histogram of residuals

Resids vs. linear pred.

Response vs. Fitted Values

7.2.2.3 Visitation GAM

```
##
## Family: binomial
## Link function: logit
##
## Formula:
## prop.visits ~ bb.ktype + s(site, by = bb.ktype, bs = "re") +
##   s(year, by = bb.ktype, bs = "re") + te(yday, elev.mean, by = bb.ktype)
##
## Parametric coefficients:
##              Estimate Std. Error z value Pr(>|z|)
## (Intercept)   -5.7028    1.0608  -5.376 7.63e-08 ***
## bb.ktypehort_5  3.2685    1.1517   2.838 0.004540 **
## bb.ktypehort_6  2.0855    1.1969   1.742 0.081450 .
## bb.ktypehort_7  0.2341    1.4590   0.160 0.872543
## bb.ktypepasc_3  1.1852    1.2548   0.945 0.344882
## bb.ktypepasc_5  4.5195    1.1023   4.100 4.13e-05 ***
## bb.ktypepasc_6  4.2698    1.1166   3.824 0.000131 ***
## bb.ktypepasc_7  0.9526    1.2111   0.787 0.431559
## bb.ktypeprat_3  1.6091    1.3410   1.200 0.230158
## bb.ktypeprat_5  2.9902    1.1423   2.618 0.008854 **
## bb.ktypeprat_6  1.4121    1.1662   1.211 0.225955
```

```

## bb.ktypeprat_7 2.6402 1.1142 2.370 0.017810 *
## bb.ktypesoro_3 3.3063 1.1458 2.886 0.003907 **
## bb.ktypesoro_5 2.4873 1.1613 2.142 0.032200 *
## bb.ktypesoro_6 1.8080 1.1418 1.584 0.113292
## bb.ktypesoro_7 3.3043 1.1275 2.931 0.003382 **
## bb.ktypetelu_3 1.2374 1.3246 0.934 0.350229
## bb.ktypetelu_5 2.4856 1.1919 2.085 0.037036 *
## bb.ktypetelu_6 2.0609 1.2773 1.614 0.106630
## bb.ktypetelu_7 2.9530 1.1124 2.655 0.007938 **
## bb.ktypewurf_3 1.6682 1.2273 1.359 0.174086
## bb.ktypewurf_5 3.3140 1.1645 2.846 0.004431 **
## bb.ktypewurf_6 3.7360 1.1253 3.320 0.000901 ***
## bb.ktypewurf_7 1.8563 1.1798 1.573 0.115641
## ---
## Signif. codes: 0 '***' 0.001 '**' 0.01 '*' 0.05 '.' 0.1 ' ' 1
##
## Approximate significance of smooth terms:
##
## edf Ref.df Chi.sq p-value
## te(yday,elev.mean):bb.ktypehort_3 7.668 9.623 9.288 0.474307
## te(yday,elev.mean):bb.ktypehort_5 11.397 13.762 65.633 < 2e-16 ***
## te(yday,elev.mean):bb.ktypehort_6 10.013 12.367 37.568 0.000244 ***
## te(yday,elev.mean):bb.ktypehort_7 8.235 10.546 17.979 0.061573 .
## te(yday,elev.mean):bb.ktypepasc_3 6.926 8.811 15.559 0.072857 .
## te(yday,elev.mean):bb.ktypepasc_5 6.656 8.436 40.217 2.56e-06 ***
## te(yday,elev.mean):bb.ktypepasc_6 11.895 14.560 47.007 2.48e-05 ***
## te(yday,elev.mean):bb.ktypepasc_7 4.223 4.979 43.551 < 2e-16 ***
## te(yday,elev.mean):bb.ktypeprat_3 10.844 12.989 44.130 4.11e-05 ***
## te(yday,elev.mean):bb.ktypeprat_5 11.809 14.466 76.810 < 2e-16 ***
## te(yday,elev.mean):bb.ktypeprat_6 4.501 5.316 12.912 0.032461 *
## te(yday,elev.mean):bb.ktypeprat_7 6.058 6.855 50.437 < 2e-16 ***
## te(yday,elev.mean):bb.ktypesoro_3 11.576 13.964 81.186 < 2e-16 ***
## te(yday,elev.mean):bb.ktypesoro_5 8.467 10.792 38.830 5.65e-05 ***
## te(yday,elev.mean):bb.ktypesoro_6 3.000 3.001 6.664 0.083443 .
## te(yday,elev.mean):bb.ktypesoro_7 5.279 6.183 29.346 4.58e-05 ***
## te(yday,elev.mean):bb.ktypetelu_3 7.836 9.732 40.063 1.33e-05 ***
## te(yday,elev.mean):bb.ktypetelu_5 9.499 11.530 49.050 4.70e-06 ***
## te(yday,elev.mean):bb.ktypetelu_6 7.754 8.500 29.309 0.000867 ***
## te(yday,elev.mean):bb.ktypetelu_7 3.580 4.029 7.463 0.114412
## te(yday,elev.mean):bb.ktypewurf_3 7.405 9.269 40.190 1.06e-05 ***
## te(yday,elev.mean):bb.ktypewurf_5 12.103 14.519 118.569 < 2e-16 ***
## te(yday,elev.mean):bb.ktypewurf_6 9.796 11.975 58.303 < 2e-16 ***
## te(yday,elev.mean):bb.ktypewurf_7 6.072 6.992 22.269 0.002312 **
## ---
## Signif. codes: 0 '***' 0.001 '**' 0.01 '*' 0.05 '.' 0.1 ' ' 1
##
## R-sq.(adj) = 0.272 Deviance explained = 33.3%
## fREML = 21522 Scale est. = 1 n = 18979

```


Histogram of residuals

Resids vs. linear pred.

Response vs. Fitted Values

7.2.3 Tabulate models

7.2.3.1 Preference GAM

```
gam_preference_s_table <- gam_preference_sum$s.table %>%
  as.data.frame() %>%
  rownames_to_column("term") %>%
  filter(str_detect(term, "te\\(")) %>%
  mutate(term = str_extract(term, ".{6}$")) %>%
  separate(term, c("bb.sp", "ktype")) %>%
  mutate(ktype = case_when(
    ktype == 3 ~ "bell",
    ktype == 5 ~ "lip",
    ktype == 6 ~ "flag",
    ktype == 7 ~ "head"
  )) %>%
  mutate(pval = signif(`p-value`, digits = 3)) %>%
  select(bb.sp, ktype, edf, pval) %>%
  as_tibble() %>%
  mutate(ktype = factor(ktype, levels = c("bell", "lip", "flag", "head")))

# Extract plotting data.
hort_3_gam_preference <- plot(sm(gam_preference, 49))$ggObj[[1]] %>%
```

```

mutate(bb.sp = rep("hort", n()),
       ktype = rep("bell", n()))

hort_5_gam_preference <- plot(sm(gam_preference, 50))$ggObj[[1]] %>%
  mutate(bb.sp = rep("hort", n()),
         ktype = rep("lip", n()))

hort_6_gam_preference <- plot(sm(gam_preference, 51))$ggObj[[1]] %>%
  mutate(bb.sp = rep("hort", n()),
         ktype = rep("flag", n()))

hort_7_gam_preference <- plot(sm(gam_preference, 52))$ggObj[[1]] %>%
  mutate(bb.sp = rep("hort", n()),
         ktype = rep("head", n()))

pasc_3_gam_preference <- plot(sm(gam_preference, 53))$ggObj[[1]] %>%
  mutate(bb.sp = rep("pasc", n()),
         ktype = rep("bell", n()))

pasc_5_gam_preference <- plot(sm(gam_preference, 54))$ggObj[[1]] %>%
  mutate(bb.sp = rep("pasc", n()),
         ktype = rep("lip", n()))

pasc_6_gam_preference <- plot(sm(gam_preference, 55))$ggObj[[1]] %>%
  mutate(bb.sp = rep("pasc", n()),
         ktype = rep("flag", n()))

pasc_7_gam_preference <- plot(sm(gam_preference, 56))$ggObj[[1]] %>%
  mutate(bb.sp = rep("pasc", n()),
         ktype = rep("head", n()))

prat_3_gam_preference <- plot(sm(gam_preference, 57))$ggObj[[1]] %>%
  mutate(bb.sp = rep("prat", n()),
         ktype = rep("bell", n()))

prat_5_gam_preference <- plot(sm(gam_preference, 58))$ggObj[[1]] %>%
  mutate(bb.sp = rep("prat", n()),
         ktype = rep("lip", n()))

prat_6_gam_preference <- plot(sm(gam_preference, 59))$ggObj[[1]] %>%
  mutate(bb.sp = rep("prat", n()),
         ktype = rep("flag", n()))

prat_7_gam_preference <- plot(sm(gam_preference, 60))$ggObj[[1]] %>%
  mutate(bb.sp = rep("prat", n()),
         ktype = rep("head", n()))

soro_3_gam_preference <- plot(sm(gam_preference, 61))$ggObj[[1]] %>%
  mutate(bb.sp = rep("soro", n()),
         ktype = rep("bell", n()))

```

```

soro_5_gam_preference <- plot(sm(gam_preference, 62))$ggObj[[1]] %>%
  mutate(bb.sp = rep("soro", n()),
         ktype = rep("lip", n()))

soro_6_gam_preference <- plot(sm(gam_preference, 63))$ggObj[[1]] %>%
  mutate(bb.sp = rep("soro", n()),
         ktype = rep("flag", n()))

soro_7_gam_preference <- plot(sm(gam_preference, 64))$ggObj[[1]] %>%
  mutate(bb.sp = rep("soro", n()),
         ktype = rep("head", n()))

telu_3_gam_preference <- plot(sm(gam_preference, 65))$ggObj[[1]] %>%
  mutate(bb.sp = rep("telu", n()),
         ktype = rep("bell", n()))

telu_5_gam_preference <- plot(sm(gam_preference, 66))$ggObj[[1]] %>%
  mutate(bb.sp = rep("telu", n()),
         ktype = rep("lip", n()))

telu_6_gam_preference <- plot(sm(gam_preference, 67))$ggObj[[1]] %>%
  mutate(bb.sp = rep("telu", n()),
         ktype = rep("flag", n()))

telu_7_gam_preference <- plot(sm(gam_preference, 68))$ggObj[[1]] %>%
  mutate(bb.sp = rep("telu", n()),
         ktype = rep("head", n()))

wurf_3_gam_preference <- plot(sm(gam_preference, 69))$ggObj[[1]] %>%
  mutate(bb.sp = rep("wurf", n()),
         ktype = rep("bell", n()))

wurf_5_gam_preference <- plot(sm(gam_preference, 70))$ggObj[[1]] %>%
  mutate(bb.sp = rep("wurf", n()),
         ktype = rep("lip", n()))

wurf_6_gam_preference <- plot(sm(gam_preference, 71))$ggObj[[1]] %>%
  mutate(bb.sp = rep("wurf", n()),
         ktype = rep("flag", n()))

wurf_7_gam_preference <- plot(sm(gam_preference, 72))$ggObj[[1]] %>%
  mutate(bb.sp = rep("wurf", n()),
         ktype = rep("head", n()))

plotting_data_gam_preference <- bind_rows(hort_3_gam_preference,
                                          hort_5_gam_preference,
                                          hort_6_gam_preference,
                                          hort_7_gam_preference,
                                          pasc_3_gam_preference,
                                          pasc_5_gam_preference,
                                          pasc_6_gam_preference,

```

```

pasc_7_gam_preference,
prat_3_gam_preference,
prat_5_gam_preference,
prat_6_gam_preference,
prat_7_gam_preference,
soro_3_gam_preference,
soro_5_gam_preference,
soro_6_gam_preference,
soro_7_gam_preference,
telu_3_gam_preference,
telu_5_gam_preference,
telu_6_gam_preference,
telu_7_gam_preference,
wurf_3_gam_preference,
wurf_5_gam_preference,
wurf_6_gam_preference,
wurf_7_gam_preference) %>%

group_by(bb.sp, ktype) %>%
mutate(z.norm = scale(z, center = FALSE),
       ktype = factor(ktype, levels = c("bell", "lip", "flag", "head")),
       date = as_date(x)) %>%
ungroup() %>%
left_join(bb_traits) %>%
left_join(gam_preference_s_table) %>%
select(z, z.norm, date, x, elevation = y, se,
       bb.sp, ktype, pbl.w, edf, pval) %>%
mutate(sig = if_else(pval < 0.05, TRUE, FALSE))

```

7.2.3.2 Flower cover GAM

```

# Tabulate model summary
gam_fl_abund_s_table <- gam_fl_abund_sum$s.table %>%
  as.data.frame() %>%
  rownames_to_column("term") %>%
  filter(str_detect(term, "te\\(")) %>%
  mutate(term = str_extract(term, ".{1}$")) %>%
  rename(ktype = term) %>%
  mutate(pval = signif(`p-value`, digits = 3)) %>%
  select(ktype, edf, pval) %>%
  as_tibble() %>%
  mutate(ktype = case_when(
    ktype == 3 ~ "bell",
    ktype == 5 ~ "lip",
    ktype == 6 ~ "flag",
    ktype == 7 ~ "head" )) %>%
  mutate(ktype = factor(ktype, levels = c("bell", "lip", "flag", "head")))

# Extract plotting data.
ktype_3_gam_fl_abund <- plot(sm(gam_fl_abund, 9))$ggObj[[1]] %>%
  mutate(ktype = rep("bell", n()))

```

```

ktype_5_gam_fl_abund <- plot(sm(gam_fl_abund, 10))$ggObj[[1]] %>%
  mutate(ktype = rep("lip", n()))

ktype_6_gam_fl_abund <- plot(sm(gam_fl_abund, 11))$ggObj[[1]] %>%
  mutate(ktype = rep("flag", n()))

ktype_7_gam_fl_abund <- plot(sm(gam_fl_abund, 12))$ggObj[[1]] %>%
  mutate(ktype = rep("head", n()))

plotting_data_gam_fl_abund <- bind_rows(ktype_3_gam_fl_abund,
                                       ktype_5_gam_fl_abund,
                                       ktype_6_gam_fl_abund,
                                       ktype_7_gam_fl_abund) %>%

  group_by(ktype) %>%
  mutate(z.norm = scale(z, center = FALSE),
         ktype = factor(ktype, levels = c("bell", "lip", "flag", "head")),
         date = as_date(x)) %>%
  ungroup() %>%
  left_join(gam_fl_abund_s_table) %>%
  select(z, z.norm, date, x, elevation = y, se,
         ktype, edf, pval) %>%
  mutate(sig = if_else(pval < 0.05, TRUE, FALSE))

```

7.2.3.3 Visitation GAM

```

# Tabulate model summary
gam_visitation_s_table <- gam_visitation_sum$s.table %>%
  as.data.frame() %>%
  rownames_to_column("term") %>%
  filter(str_detect(term, "te\\(")) %>%
  mutate(term = str_extract(term, ".{6}$")) %>%
  separate(term, c("bb.sp", "ktype")) %>%
  mutate(pval = signif(`p-value`, digits = 3)) %>%
  select(bb.sp, ktype, edf, pval) %>%
  as_tibble() %>%
  mutate(ktype = case_when(
    ktype == 3 ~ "bell",
    ktype == 5 ~ "lip",
    ktype == 6 ~ "flag",
    ktype == 7 ~ "head" )) %>%
  mutate(ktype = factor(ktype, levels = c("bell", "lip", "flag", "head")))

# Extract plotting data.
hort_3_gam_visitation <- plot(sm(gam_visitation, 49))$ggObj[[1]] %>%
  mutate(bb.sp = rep("hort", n()),
         ktype = rep("bell", n()))

hort_5_gam_visitation <- plot(sm(gam_visitation, 50))$ggObj[[1]] %>%
  mutate(bb.sp = rep("hort", n()),
         ktype = rep("lip", n()))

```

```

hort_6_gam_visitation <- plot(sm(gam_visitation, 51))$ggObj[[1]] %>%
  mutate(bb.sp = rep("hort", n()),
         ktype = rep("flag", n()))

hort_7_gam_visitation <- plot(sm(gam_visitation, 52))$ggObj[[1]] %>%
  mutate(bb.sp = rep("hort", n()),
         ktype = rep("head", n()))

pasc_3_gam_visitation <- plot(sm(gam_visitation, 53))$ggObj[[1]] %>%
  mutate(bb.sp = rep("pasc", n()),
         ktype = rep("bell", n()))

pasc_5_gam_visitation <- plot(sm(gam_visitation, 54))$ggObj[[1]] %>%
  mutate(bb.sp = rep("pasc", n()),
         ktype = rep("lip", n()))

pasc_6_gam_visitation <- plot(sm(gam_visitation, 55))$ggObj[[1]] %>%
  mutate(bb.sp = rep("pasc", n()),
         ktype = rep("flag", n()))

pasc_7_gam_visitation <- plot(sm(gam_visitation, 56))$ggObj[[1]] %>%
  mutate(bb.sp = rep("pasc", n()),
         ktype = rep("head", n()))

prat_3_gam_visitation <- plot(sm(gam_visitation, 57))$ggObj[[1]] %>%
  mutate(bb.sp = rep("prat", n()),
         ktype = rep("bell", n()))

prat_5_gam_visitation <- plot(sm(gam_visitation, 58))$ggObj[[1]] %>%
  mutate(bb.sp = rep("prat", n()),
         ktype = rep("lip", n()))

prat_6_gam_visitation <- plot(sm(gam_visitation, 59))$ggObj[[1]] %>%
  mutate(bb.sp = rep("prat", n()),
         ktype = rep("flag", n()))

prat_7_gam_visitation <- plot(sm(gam_visitation, 60))$ggObj[[1]] %>%
  mutate(bb.sp = rep("prat", n()),
         ktype = rep("head", n()))

soro_3_gam_visitation <- plot(sm(gam_visitation, 61))$ggObj[[1]] %>%
  mutate(bb.sp = rep("soro", n()),
         ktype = rep("bell", n()))

soro_5_gam_visitation <- plot(sm(gam_visitation, 62))$ggObj[[1]] %>%
  mutate(bb.sp = rep("soro", n()),
         ktype = rep("lip", n()))

soro_6_gam_visitation <- plot(sm(gam_visitation, 63))$ggObj[[1]] %>%
  mutate(bb.sp = rep("soro", n()),

```

```

      ktype = rep("flag", n()))

soro_7_gam_visitation <- plot(sm(gam_visitation, 64))$ggObj[[1]] %>%
  mutate(bb.sp = rep("soro", n()),
         ktype = rep("head", n()))

telu_3_gam_visitation <- plot(sm(gam_visitation, 65))$ggObj[[1]] %>%
  mutate(bb.sp = rep("telu", n()),
         ktype = rep("bell", n()))

telu_5_gam_visitation <- plot(sm(gam_visitation, 66))$ggObj[[1]] %>%
  mutate(bb.sp = rep("telu", n()),
         ktype = rep("lip", n()))

telu_6_gam_visitation <- plot(sm(gam_visitation, 67))$ggObj[[1]] %>%
  mutate(bb.sp = rep("telu", n()),
         ktype = rep("flag", n()))

telu_7_gam_visitation <- plot(sm(gam_visitation, 68))$ggObj[[1]] %>%
  mutate(bb.sp = rep("telu", n()),
         ktype = rep("head", n()))

wurf_3_gam_visitation <- plot(sm(gam_visitation, 69))$ggObj[[1]] %>%
  mutate(bb.sp = rep("wurf", n()),
         ktype = rep("bell", n()))

wurf_5_gam_visitation <- plot(sm(gam_visitation, 70))$ggObj[[1]] %>%
  mutate(bb.sp = rep("wurf", n()),
         ktype = rep("lip", n()))

wurf_6_gam_visitation <- plot(sm(gam_visitation, 71))$ggObj[[1]] %>%
  mutate(bb.sp = rep("wurf", n()),
         ktype = rep("flag", n()))

wurf_7_gam_visitation <- plot(sm(gam_visitation, 72))$ggObj[[1]] %>%
  mutate(bb.sp = rep("wurf", n()),
         ktype = rep("head", n()))

plotting_data_gam_visitation <- bind_rows(hort_3_gam_visitation,
                                          hort_5_gam_visitation,
                                          hort_6_gam_visitation,
                                          hort_7_gam_visitation,
                                          pasc_3_gam_visitation,
                                          pasc_5_gam_visitation,
                                          pasc_6_gam_visitation,
                                          pasc_7_gam_visitation,
                                          prat_3_gam_visitation,
                                          prat_5_gam_visitation,
                                          prat_6_gam_visitation,
                                          prat_7_gam_visitation,
                                          soro_3_gam_visitation,

```

```

soro_5_gam_visitation,
soro_6_gam_visitation,
soro_7_gam_visitation,
telu_3_gam_visitation,
telu_5_gam_visitation,
telu_6_gam_visitation,
telu_7_gam_visitation,
wurf_3_gam_visitation,
wurf_5_gam_visitation,
wurf_6_gam_visitation,
wurf_7_gam_visitation) %>%

group_by(bb.sp, ktype) %>%
mutate(z.norm = scale(z, center = FALSE),
       ktype = factor(ktype, levels = c("bell", "lip", "flag", "head")),
       date = as_date(x)) %>%
ungroup() %>%
left_join(bb_traits) %>%
left_join(gam_visitation_s_table) %>%
select(z, z.norm, date, x, elevation = y, se,
       bb.sp, ktype, pbl.w, edf, pval) %>%
mutate(sig = if_else(pval < 0.05, TRUE, FALSE))

```

7.2.4 Plot models

```

ggplot(plotting_data__gam_preference, aes(date, elevation, z = z.norm, fill = z.norm)) +
  geom_raster() +
  geom_contour(color = "black",
              size = 0.1,
              bins = 40,
              aes(linetype = sig)) + # by fixing bins, we scale contours to
                                     # each plot while letting the color ramp
                                     # represent differences in scale across
                                     # plots; I think this is a good compromise

  facet_grid(reorder(bb.sp, -pbl.w) ~ ktype) +
  scale_linetype_manual(values = c("dotted", "solid"))+
  scale_fill_viridis_c(na.value = "transparent") +
  labs(x = NULL, y = "Elevation (m)", fill = "Normalized\neffect", linetype = "p < 0.05") +
  theme_light(12) +
  theme(panel.grid = element_blank(),
        axis.text.x = element_text(angle = 90, vjust = 0.5))

```



```

ggplot(plotting_data_gam_fl_abund, aes(date, elevation, z = z.norm, fill = z.norm)) +
  geom_raster() +
  geom_contour(color = "black",
              size = 0.1,
              bins = 40) +
  facet_wrap(~ktype) +
  scale_fill_viridis_c(na.value = "transparent") +
  labs(x = NULL, y = "Elevation (m)", fill = "Normalized\neffect", linetype = "p < 0.05") +
  theme_light(12) +
  theme(panel.grid = element_blank(),
        axis.text.x = element_text(angle = 90, vjust = 0.5))

```



```
ggplot(plotting_data_gam_visitation, aes(date, elevation, z = z.norm, fill = z.norm)) +
  geom_raster() +
  geom_contour(color = "black",
              size = 0.1,
              bins = 40,
              aes(linetype = sig)) +
  facet_grid(reorder(bb.sp, -pbl.w) ~ ktype) +
  scale_linetype_manual(values = c("dotted", "solid"))+
  scale_fill_viridis_c(na.value = "transparent") +
  labs(x = NULL, y = "Elevation (m)", fill = "Normalized\neffect", linetype = "p < 0.05") +
  theme_light(12) +
  theme(panel.grid = element_blank(),
        axis.text.x = element_text(angle = 90, vjust = 0.5))
```


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